

GHRSSST RDAC

NAVAL OCEANOGRAPHIC OFFICE

Naval Oceanographic Office Regional Data Assembly Center

GHR SST Science Team Meeting XXI 1 – 4 June 2020

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NAVOCEANO GHR SST data provided to JPL PODAAC

L2P GDSV2.0

- NOAA-19 global 8.8 km & regional 2.2km
- MetOp-A/B global 8.8 km
- S-NPP VIIRS global 750 m

L4 GDSV2.0

- K10 global 10 km

GHR SST data acquired by NAVOCEANO

- MSG 1/4 SEVIRI L3C from OSISAF acquired from PODAAC (Assimilated in Navy GOFS)
- GCOM-W AMSR2_NRT from JAXA (Assimilated in Navy GOFS)
- Sentinel-3A/B SLSTR L2P from EUMETSAT via NOAA STAR's terrestrial EUMETCAST feed

Future NAVOCEANO GHR SST data

- NOAA-20 VIIRS Global 750 m L2P is ready – **Does anyone want this?**
- MetOp-C global 8.8 km using improved SST processing (SST 2.6) available July 2020
 - Doubles the number of SST retrievals, but no increase in L2P file size
- MetOp-A/B processing to be updated to SST 2.6 when users are ready
- GOES-13 9km over the Indian Ocean by end of 2020 - **Does anyone want this?**
- Implement ONR MISST-3 high latitude developments in 2021

Approved for public release; distribution unlimited.

Updates

SST V2.6 processing upgrade

- Correct formatting of large numbers
- Reduce data flow by eliminating input channels not used in SST routines
- New module for error handling in module reading aerosol files
- Made new AVHRR cloud parameter files
- New reflectance tables for the ref2d test
- New coefficients for the 4 μ m test, code to handle cases with coefficients missing
- Added twilight parameter (when SZA > 80 degrees) to the AVHRR and VIIRS processing
 - Makes use of the 4 μ m brightness temperature test during twilight conditions
 - Logging is included to know how much is considered twilight, and the percentage of twilight data that is caught by the 4 μ m test
- Added ability for HYCOM SST/ice data to be used instead of K10 field
- Code is/will be used for both VIIRS and AVHRR